

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation of Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable D 3.2

Baseline simulation results and assessment

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1. Executive Summary

The work presented in this current deliverable DO3.2 has been carried out in the framework of the collaboration agreement between OPEUS and the S2R Members project FINE1 (Grant agreement No. 730818).

The main objective of this deliverable is to elaborate energy-baseline simulation results for the pre-defined reference scenarios. These baseline simulation results were calculated with the OPEUS-tool, which was developed within OPEUS WP2. The baseline scenarios, including the environmental conditions, the track data as well as the implemented train parameters are defined within the OPEUS deliverable D3.1 “Baseline scenario set up” and the FINE1 deliverable D3.1 “Energy baseline”.

This current report summarises the simulation results for the defined reference scenarios and gives a short assessment of the resulting energy consumptions.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronyms	Description
ESS	Energy Storage System
FINE1	Shift2Rail partner project: Future Improvement for Energy and Noise – Grant Agreement number: 730818
FrMain	Freight Mainline service
HS300	High Speed 300 service
HS250	High Speed 250 service
IC	Intercity service
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
Reg160	Regional 160 service
Reg140	Regional 140 service
Suburb	Suburban service
WP	Work package

3. List of Symbols

Symbol	Description
E_{rec}	Recuperated energy at the catenary
E_{cons}	Consumed energy at the catenary
f_{load}	Load factor
f_{rec}	Recuperation factor
n_{pax}	Number of traveling passengers
$n_{pax,total}$	Total Capacity of passengers per train
n_{seat}	Number of seats
s_{total}	Total travel distance
t_{allout}	Travel time with all-out operation
t_{end}	Desired time to reach the next station
$t_{timetable}$	Travel time according to the timetable
v_{lim}	Current speed limit
v_d	Desired velocity

4. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D3.2 “Baseline simulation results and assessment” in the framework of the WP 3, task 3.2 (Scenario simulations) of OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015).

It contributes as well to WP4, task 4.5 (Evaluation of Energy KPI - interim) of FINE1 (S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015).

5. Objective/Aim

This document has been prepared to provide the simulation results of the baseline scenarios defined within WP 3, task 3.1 of OPEUS (D3.1 “Scenario Set Up”) and WP 3, task 3.1 of FINE1 (D3.1 “Energy Baseline”)

The results presented in the current deliverable serve as a reference for the following work within OPEUS WP 3, task 3.2 (Scenario Simulations), OPEUS WP4, task 4.2 (DAS related strategies model-based assessment), WP5, task 5.2 (Analysis of energy losses in the traction chain), OPEUS WP 6, task 6.2 (Advanced ESSs study - Critical innovative technologies assessment). Furthermore, this work is closely linked to FINE1 D4.5 “Evaluation of Energy KPI - interim”, FINE1 D4.6 “Evaluation of Energy KPI - update” and FINE1 D4.7 “Evaluation of Energy KPI - final”.

6. Introduction

The objective of WP3 is the evaluation of energy simulations for various pre-defined scenarios. Those simulation results serve as a reliable basis for the assessment of technical innovations regarding energy consumptions and energy savings.

To perform these energy simulations, the OPEUS-tool was developed within OPEUS *WP2 – Simulation model and tool development* (see [3], [4]). This tool enables the user to calculate the energy consumption for various train, track and operational scenarios. It uses a backward simulation approach to determine the required power profiles according to a given speed profile. These power profiles will be determined for single components of the traction chain (e.g. power profile at the motor level, power profile at the transformer level) as well as for the total power at the energy delivery point.

In cooperation with the Shift2Rail member project FINE1 (Future Improvement for Energy and Noise – Grant Agreement number: 730818), various reference scenarios were defined (see [2], [1]). The simulation results for these reference scenarios serve as a baseline to assess the technical innovations achieved within Shift2Rail. Section 7 provides a summary of these agreed baseline scenarios.

Section 8 includes the actual simulation results, while Section 9 assesses these reference results.

7. Definition of baseline scenarios

The reference scenarios for the energy baseline were defined within the corporate work by FINE1 and OPEUS. This baseline definition is based partially on previous projects (e.g. Roll2Rail and CleanER-D) and the draft standard prEN50951.

The working group agreed to perform simulations for the following service categories:

- High-Speed service:
 - High Speed 300
 - High Speed 250
 - Intercity
- Regional service:
 - Regional 160
 - Regional 140
- Urban service
 - Suburban
 - Metro
 - Tram
- Freight service

The deliverable reports [1] and [2] provide detailed descriptions of the baseline definition for these service categories. Especially, these reports focus on the definition of the track data (e.g. speed limits, timetable, tunnel profile, curve profile), the parametrisation of the train characteristic (esp. refer to [2]) as well as further boundary conditions (e.g. utilisation of special components, environmental conditions).

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the most important boundary conditions to characterise the baseline scenarios. This summary helps to understand and to classify the simulation results presented in Section 8.

Baseline scenario characteristic	
Track data	According to agreed service profiles (see [1], [2])
Train data	According to defined parameter sets } see [2] According to defined efficiency maps }
ESS	No ESS (see [2])
Traction components	Induction motor } see [2] IGBT converter } Common transformer }
Environmental conditions	No head-wind } see [2] No influence of ambient temperature }

<p>Trajectory mode</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coasting enabled – refer to green curve in Figure 1: Generic driving cycle (exceptions possible!): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Acceleration with max. acceleration (limited by max. traction effort and passenger comfort) until speed limit is reached Cruising (const. speed), if necessary Coasting to fulfil the time-table Braking with max. deceleration (limited by max. braking effort and passenger comfort) <div data-bbox="555 719 1243 1102" data-label="Figure"> </div> <p>Figure 1: Possible trajectory modes</p>
<p>Operational strategy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No load distribution between single traction drives No partial switch-off of single traction drives
<p>Auxiliary connection</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Auxiliary load is connected to the DC intermediate circuit for all service categories
<p>Season mode</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation of spring/autumn, summer/winter season Document in detail for spring/autumn case Document results overview at least on the same level as KPI (kWh/km) for both (spring/autumn, summer/winter) cases

Table 1: Boundary conditions for baseline scenarios

As indicated in Table 1, Section 8 below presents the detailed simulation results (e.g. power profiles) only for the spring/autumn season (which has effects on the auxiliary load power). Nevertheless, for the assessment of the results, Section 9 also includes the simulation results for the summer and winter seasons.

8. Simulation results for baseline scenarios

The objective of the current section is the visualisation of the simulation results for the defined service categories. The simulation results are summarised in a very high degree of detail within the single output files of the OPEUS-tool. These results are also included within the tool itself (please refer to the download link given on the initial page of this document).

The following subsections enable access to the analysis of these simulation results and provide an understandable overview of the simulation results within the current report. To assess the energy results, the velocity profile, as well as the power profile at the energy delivery point, will be depicted for the single service categories. In addition to these time-based characteristics, the total energy budget is summarized for various levels of the traction chain (e.g. motor level, DC circuit level, catenary).

8.1. Baseline simulation results for High-Speed service

This subsection presents the baseline simulation results for the High-Speed service. In particular, the High-Speed service is separated into High Speed 300, High Speed 250 and Intercity. The velocity profiles, as well as the power profiles at the catenary, are depicted in Figure 2 - HS300, Figure 3 - HS250 and Figure 4 - Intercity.

Figure 2: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for High Speed 300 service

Figure 3: Speed profile and power profile at the catenary for High Speed 250 service

Figure 4: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Intercity service

Although the velocity profile for the first section is the same for HS300 and HS250, the maximum power at the catenary is different. This is mainly caused by different definitions of the running resistance as well as different traction effort for both trains (see [2]).

Table 2 provides an overview of the evaluated energies for the three different High-Speed service categories.

Service Category	Unit	HS300	HS250	Intercity
<i>total time</i>	s	6600	7560	9720
<i>total time</i>	h	01:50:00	02:06:00	02:42:00
<i>total distance</i>	km	300	300	250
<i>commercial speed</i>	km/h	164	143	93
<i>traction energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	3502	2950	1197
<i>total braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	152	762	296
<i>ED-braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	122	356	287
<i>braking energy at the mechanical brakes</i>	kWh	31	405	8
<i>traction energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	4016	3513	1477
<i>recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	99	305	237
<i>auxiliary energy at the DC link</i>	kWh	550	595	522
<i>rheostat braking energy at DC link</i>	kWh	0	0	0
<i>consumed energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	5136	4555	2215
<i>recuperated energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	83	255	189
<i>recuperation factor E_{rec}/E_{cons}</i>	%	1,6	6	9
<i>number of seats</i>	-	460	460	300
<i>number of pax</i>	-	360	360	240
<i>consumption per kilometre</i>	Wh/km	16842	14336	8104

<i>consumption per passenger-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/pax	47	40	34
<i>consumption per seat-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/seat	37	31	27

Table 2: Baseline simulation results for High Speed service

8.2. Baseline simulation results for Regional service

This subsection presents the baseline simulation results for the Regional service. In particular, the Regional service is separated into Regional 160 and Regional 140.

The velocity profiles, as well as the power profiles at the catenary, are depicted in Figure 5 – Reg160 and Figure 6 – Reg140.

Figure 5: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Regional 160 service

Figure 6: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Regional 140 service

The figures above underline the most important differences between the two pre-defined Regional service profiles: The maximum speed and the total travelling (Regional 160 is defined for a 250km distance, as the Regional 140 profile is determined with a 70km route length).

Table 3 provides an overview of the evaluated energies for the two different Regional service categories.

Service Category	Unit	Reg160	Reg140
<i>total time</i>	s	10800	4260
<i>total time</i>	h	03:00:00	01:11:00
<i>total distance</i>	km	250	70
<i>commercial speed</i>	km/h	83	59
<i>traction energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	724	258
<i>total braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	171	137
<i>ED-braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	170	135
<i>braking energy at the mechanical brakes</i>	kWh	1	2

<i>traction energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	942	332
<i>recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	139	111
<i>auxiliary energy at the DC link</i>	kWh	450	176
<i>rheostat braking energy at DC link</i>	kWh	0	0
<i>consumed energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	1564	576
<i>recuperated energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	110	90
<i>recuperation factor E_{rec}/E_{cons}</i>	%	7	16
<i>number of seats</i>	-	230	230
<i>number of pax</i>	-	180	180
<i>consumption per kilometre</i>	Wh/km	5816	6946
<i>consumption per passenger-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/pax	32	39
<i>consumption per seat-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/seat	25	30

Table 3: Baseline simulation results for Regional service

8.3. Baseline simulation results for Urban service

This subsection presents the baseline simulation results for the Urban service. In particular, the Urban service is separated into Suburban, Metro and Tram.

The velocity profiles, as well as the power profiles at the energy delivery point, are depicted in Figure 7 - Suburban, Figure 8 - Metro and Figure 9 - Tram.

Figure 7: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Suburban service

Figure 8: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Metro service

Figure 9: Speed profile and power profile at catenary for Tram service* (*simulated with updated track data in OPEUS tool V7)

The speed profile of the Tram service (see Figure 9) emphasises the peculiarities of the Tram service profile. In contrast to all other service categories, the Tram service profile contains operational stops, which are defined as “zero-second-stops” - braking until standstill followed by an immediate acceleration (e.g. see Figure 9, $t \approx 200s$). These operation stops represent traffic conditions like red light signals at junctions or congestion in mixed traffic alignments.

Table 4 provides an overview of the evaluated energies for the three different Urban service categories.

<i>Service Category</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Suburban</i>	<i>Metro</i>	<i>Tram*</i> <i>*simulated with updated track data in OPEUS tool V7</i>
<i>total time</i>	s	2640	2280	1780
<i>total time</i>	h	00:44:00	00:38:00	00:29:40
<i>total distance</i>	km	40	21.5	10.7
<i>commercial speed</i>	km/h	55	34	22
<i>traction energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	425	250	29
<i>total braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	291	217	23

<i>ED-braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	285	199	23
<i>braking energy at the mechanical brakes</i>	kWh	6	18	0
<i>traction energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	518	313	39
<i>recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	241	169	19
<i>auxiliary energy at the DC link</i>	kWh	113	114	33
<i>rheostat braking energy at DC link</i>	kWh	0	0	0
<i>consumed energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	717	418	69
<i>recuperated energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	208	150	15
<i>recuperation factor E_{rec}/E_{cons}</i>	%	29	36	21
<i>number of seats</i>	-	200	186	64
<i>number of pax</i>	-	160	1000	200
<i>consumption per kilometre</i>	Wh/km	12722	12474	5031
<i>consumption per passenger-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/pax	80	12	25
<i>consumption per seat-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/seat	64	67	79

Table 4: Baseline simulation results for Urban service

8.4. Baseline simulation results for Freight service

This subsection presents the baseline simulation results for the Freight Mainline service. Figure 10 shows the velocity profile as well as the power profile at the catenary level. The Freight Mainline service is the only pre-defined service category considering an altitude profile along the track. This altitude profile is also depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Gradient, speed profile and power profile at catenary for Freight Mainline service

The power profile in Figure 10 shows the effect of the included altitude profile: For a positive gradient ($t \approx 5800s \dots 7800s$), the required traction power increases, whereas for a negative gradient ($t \approx 8800s \dots 10200s$), the train allows for recuperation even during cruising. Table 5 provides an overview of the evaluated energies for the Freight Mainline service category.

Service Category	Unit	Freight Mainline
<i>total time</i>	s	15615
<i>total time</i>	h	04:20:15
<i>total distance</i>	m	300000
<i>commercial speed</i>	km/h	69
<i>traction energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	3967
<i>total braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	846
<i>ED-braking energy at the wheel</i>	kWh	777
<i>braking energy at the mechanical brakes</i>	kWh	69

<i>traction energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	4703
<i>recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link</i>	kWh	668
<i>auxiliary energy at the DC link</i>	kWh	282
<i>rheostat braking energy at DC link</i>	kWh	0
<i>consumed energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	5556
<i>recuperated energy at the catenary</i>	kWh	593
<i>recuperation factor E_{rec}/E_{cons}</i>	%	11
<i>Payload</i>	tonne	1026
<i>consumption per kilometre</i>	Wh/km	16543
<i>consumption per tonne-kilometre</i>	Wh/km/tonne	16

Table 5: Baseline simulation results for Freight service

9. Assessment of baseline simulation results

The main objective of the following section is to enable an assessment of the simulation results given in Section 8. Therefore this section provides various opportunities to analyse the different results, e.g. a reflection regarding time composition concerning the different driving modes, an analysis of the recuperation factor $f_{rec} = \frac{E_{cons}}{E_{rec}}$ (the ratio between the total consumed energy E_{cons} and the total recuperated energy E_{rec}) as well as a study of the most important performance indicators (Wh per km, Wh per seat-km, Wh per pax-km, Wh per ton-km).

To help the reader with getting an impression of the impact of the time-table, most of the results will be compared against the allout drivecycle (minimum driving time, depending on the traction effort of the vehicle).

Figure 11 shows the total time and the commercial speed for all service categories for the allout mode as well as for the time-table drivecycle. The ratio between allout time and total travel time according to the timetable indicates the potential of an optimal driving strategy (e.g. in case of DAS, ATO – OPEUS WP4). According to Table 6, this time margin is about 5% (HS250) up to 16% (Reg140).

	HS300	HS250	IC	Reg 160	Reg 140	Suburb	Metro	Tram	Freight Main
$\frac{t_{timetable}}{t_{allout}}$	1,086	1,047	1,064	1,113	1,149	1,082	1,091	1,057	1,132

Table 6: Time ratio between the timetable travelling time and allout travelling time

Figure 11: Total time as well as commercial speed for various service categories

Corresponding to the baseline definition, the driving strategy utilizes coasting to fulfil the timetable (see Table 1). An investigation of the composition of the driving cycle regarding the utilisation of the different driving modes contributes to a better understanding of the correlation between the energy consumption and the implemented driving strategy. Figure 12 presents the total traveling time partitioned into the single time periods used for the various driving modes. Obvious are the large shares in coasting, which are not included within the allout mode driving cycles. Compared to allout mode, the acceleration time as well as the braking time is decreased for the utilization of the timetable driving profile, which has an enormous impact on the energy savings.

Figure 12: Time composition concerning the utilisation of the driving modes

An important parameter to assess the energy consumption of railway vehicles is the recuperation factor, which provides an information about the ratio between the total consumed energy and the total recuperated energy at the catenary level. Figure 13 provides an overview of the single recuperation factor. This includes the result for both the auxiliary load power during the summer/winter season as well as the auxiliary load during the spring/autumn season. Additionally, the recuperation factor for the allout mode (spring season) is included to show the impact of coasting.

The resulting recuperation factor varies significantly. It attains small values of about $\approx 2\%$ - 5% for High-Speed applications but up to $\approx 20\%$ - 35% for Urban service. This wide variation is mainly caused by the different numbers of stations, which correlate to the number of braking processes.*

Another reason is the parametrisation of the effort of the electro-dynamical braking. In the case of High-Speed, it is not possible to apply braking with the maximum motor power for very high train speeds (a lot of braking energy has to be delivered via the mechanical brakes – esp. for HS250, see Table 2).

* Note: For real train operation the density of trains per subsection/section also effects this result (e.g. up to 40 trains per hour per direction in metros). Though, the OPEUS-tool only considers single train operation.

Compared to the allout mode, the recuperation factor is even lower. This is caused by the utilisation of coasting, which leads to a lower velocity (less kinetic energy) of the train during braking.

Figure 13: Recuperation factor for the single service categories

The next subsection of this report focuses on the presentation and analysis of the most important energy performance indicators, namely:

- Energy consumption per km (Wh/km),
 - energy consumption per seat-km (Wh/seat-km),
 - energy consumption per passenger-km (Wh/pax-km)
- as well as
- energy consumption per tonne-km (Wh/tonne-km).

Via post-processing of the simulation results from the OPEUS-tool, it is possible to derive these energy performance indicators.

In analogy to the presentation of the recuperation factor, these indicators are summarized for all 4 seasons as well as for the allout mode (spring/autumn only).

Figure 15 depicts the total energy consumption per km according to

$$\frac{E_{cons} - E_{rec}}{s_{total}} \quad (1)$$

Corresponding to the equation above, the consumption per km represents the deviation between the total consumed energy E_{cons} and the total recuperated energy E_{rec} , divided by the total traveling distance s_{total} .

The energy consumption for the baseline scenarios is within the range of $\approx 5000\text{Wh/km}$ (for Tram) and $\approx 17500\text{Wh/km}$ (for Freight).

Figure 14: Energy consumption per km (Wh/km) for the single service categories

For the passenger transport services (High-Speed, Regional, Urban), the specific energy consumption is given in Wh/seat-km or with Wh/pax-km, whereas for the Freight service, the unit Wh/tonne-km is chosen to denote the specific energy consumption (see [5]). To assess the indicators regarding seat-km and pax-km, it is sensible to introduce the passenger load factor f_{load} , which is given by

$$f_{load} = \frac{n_{pax}}{n_{pax,total}} \quad (1)$$

Here n_{pax} is the total number of traveling passengers per train and $n_{pax,total}$ represents the total capacity of passengers per train.*

The resulting load factors for the passenger transport service are summarized within Table 7.

	HS300	HS250	IC	Reg 160	Reg 140	Suburb	Metro	Tram
n_{seat}	460	460	300	230	230	200	186	64
$n_{pax,total}$	460	460	300	230	230	200	1000*	200*
n_{pax}	360	360	240	180	180	160	1000*	200*
load factor	0,78	0,78	0,80	0,78	0,78	0,80	1*	1*

Table 7: Passenger load factors for single service categories

* Note: The total passenger capacity $n_{pax,total}$ for Metro and Tram presented in Table 7, is composed of both the total number of seating persons and the total number of standing persons – e.g. an occupancy of 64 total seats plus 4 persons per m² standing, leads to a total capacity of 200 persons for a 32m Tram). Accordingly, the determined load factors are representing rush-hour operation with a 100% occupancy rate, (sometimes beyond: 6pax/ m²). On average over the 18 hours of operation and 7 days/week, the load factor typically would range from 20-40 % for Tram and Metros. Therefore, the energy performance (Wh/pax-km) described in the deliverable should be understood as the performance in the most favourable scenario, and not be compared to those of the HS and regional mode.

Almost every service category has a load factor of $f_{load} = 0,78 \dots 0,8$, which means that there are about 25%-28% more seats than passengers. For the urban personal transport, this ratio is inverted: There are a lot more passengers than seats, which leads to a load factor $f_{load} > 1$. This parametrisation shall be kept in mind during the analysis of the following performance indicators.

Figure 15 and Figure 16 represent the specific energy consumption for the passenger transport service. For the High Speed and Regional service, the specific consumption is in a range of about $\approx 25\text{Wh}/\text{seat-km} \dots 40\text{Wh}/\text{seat-km}$, or in a range of about $\approx 35\text{Wh}/\text{pax-km} \dots 50\text{Wh}/\text{pax-km}$, respectively. Nevertheless, the Urban transport service has a higher energy per seat indicator ($\approx 60\text{Wh}/\text{seat-km} \dots 80\text{Wh}/\text{seat-km}$). This is caused by the specific characteristic of the urban drive cycles - e.g. more stops lead to more acceleration and braking procedures. Moreover, the Urban service profiles allow for a higher acceleration/deceleration (see [2]), which also has positive effect on the total energy consumption.

Figure 15: Energy consumption per seat-km (Wh/seat-km) for the single service categories

Figure 16: Energy consumption per pax-km (Wh/pax-km) for the single service categories

As mentioned above, the impact of the passenger load factor is underlined by the results shown in Figure 16. The Metro and Tram service has a comparatively low specific energy consumption per passenger, caused by a high load factor.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable report summarizes the reference energy simulation results for the pre-defined service categories as defined within [1] and [2]. These energy simulations were executed with the OPEUS-tool, which was developed within OPEUS WP2.

The results presented in this deliverable, serve as a baseline for further comparisons with future Shift2Rail innovations.

Furthermore, this document provides an approach for the assessment and analyses of the simulation results and, especially, the determined energy consumptions.

11. References

- [1] R. Palacin, „OPEUS Deliverable DO3.1 - Scenario Set Up and Discription,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2017.
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12. Appendices

Appendix A – Detailed baseline simulation results

For a more detailed view on the simulation results, please refer to the download link of the OPEUS-tool (Please find the link on the first page of this document). The baseline scenario simulations are included within the tool for an easy comparison of the energy consumption achieved by technical innovations.